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Strain sensing of epoxy resin using porous Carbon nanotube/Graphene composite buckypaper

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Strain measurement

Graphene/Carbon nanotube Buckypaper(GCBP) strain gauge

Traditional metal strain gauge

High stability

Low cost

Low sensitivity

Unidirectionality

Non-embeddability

Embeddability

Multidirectional

High conductivity

Flexibility

High sensitivity

Piezoresistive properties of the CBP and GCBP

Fig.(a) Testing of the piezoresistive properties of GCBPs

Fig. (b) The curves of σ and $\Delta R/R_0\%$ versus ε for CNT BPs

Fig. (c) The curves of σ and $\Delta R/R_0\%$ versus ε for GCBPs

- The CBP exhibits a relatively long stage I and the corresponding ε is calculated as 1.35%. This is because entangled and meandering CNTs restrict the change of conductive network.
- Surface-to-surface based slipping within the GNP network will cause a larger change of contact area, which is greater than that of point-to-point based slipping within the CNT network.

Piezoresistive properties of the CBP and GCBP

In-situ strain sensing capability of GCBP

GF is increased by 441% compared with the traditional metal strain gauges!

Repeatable, Non-hysteresis!

Fig. The response of $\Delta R/R_0\%$ versus time (T) of the GCBP measured under applied cyclic and stepwise strains

Long-term cyclic tension-compression loading (10h, 1000 cycles) is applied with a strain range from -0.3% to 0.3%.

Excellent stability!

Conclusion

**These excellent strain sensing performances
make it potential in the field of structural health monitoring!**